

1 **Monte Carlo method for Predicting of Cardiac Toxicity:**
2 **hERG blocker compounds**

3
4 Marco Gobbi¹, Marten Beeg¹, Mariya A. Toropova^{1,2}, Andrey A. Toropov^{3,*}, Mario Salmona⁴

5
6 ¹ *Department of Molecular Biochemistry and Pharmacology, Laboratory of Pharmacodynamics and*
7 *Pharmacokinetics, IRCCS-Istituto di Ricerche Farmacologiche Mario Negri, Via La Masa 19, 20156*
8 *Milano, Italy*

9 ² *Dipartimento di Scienze Farmaceutiche, Università degli Studi di Milano, Via L. Mangiagalli, 25,*
10 *20133 Milan, Italy*

11 ³ *Department of Environmental Health Science, Laboratory of Environmental Chemistry and*
12 *Toxicology, IRCCS-Istituto di Ricerche Farmacologiche Mario Negri, Via La Masa 19, 20156 Milano,*
13 *Italy*

14 ⁴ *Department of Molecular Biochemistry and Pharmacology, Laboratory of Biochemistry and Protein*
15 *Chemistry, IRCCS-Istituto di Ricerche Farmacologiche Mario Negri, Via La Masa 19, 20156 Milano,*
16 *Italy*

17
18
19 **Published version of this paper could be find here** <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.toxlet.2016.04.010>

20 **Toxicology Letters Volumes 250–251, 27 May 2016, Pages 42-46**
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33

Abstract

The estimation of the cardiotoxicity of compounds is important task for the drug discovery as well as for the risk assessment in ecological aspect. The experimental estimation of the above endpoint is complex and expensive. Hence, the theoretical computational methods are very attractive alternative of the direct experiment. A model for cardiac toxicity of 400 hERG blocker compounds (pIC_{50}) is built up using the Monte Carlo method. Three different splits into the visible training set (in fact, the training set plus the calibration set) and invisible validation sets examined. The predictive potential is very good for all examined splits. The statistical characteristics for the external validation set are (i) the coefficient of determination $r^2 = (0.90-0.93)$; and (ii) root-mean squared error $s = (0.30-0.40)$.

Keywords: Monte Carlo method; Cardiac toxicity; QSAR; OECD principles; CORAL software

Corresponding author:

Laboratory of Environmental Chemistry and Toxicology,

IRCCS - Istituto di Ricerche Farmacologiche Mario Negri, Via La Masa 19, 20156 Milano, Italy

Tel: +39 02 3901 4595

Fax: +3902 3901 4735

Email: andrey.toropov@marionegri.it

79 1. Introduction

80 Identification of potential human Ether-a-go-go Related-Gene (hERG) potassium channel blockers is very
81 important task of the drug discovery and drug safety process in pharmaceutical industries as well as for
82 academic drug discovery centers. Recent works suggest starting to address such issues at the hit selection
83 stage (Park et al., 2013; Anwar-Mohamed et al., 2014; Villoutreix and Taboureau, 2015).

84 In order to prioritize molecules during the early drug discovery phase and to reduce the risk of the
85 preliminary checking up of pharmaceutical agents, the computational approaches have been developed to
86 predict the potential of hERG blockage of new drug candidates (Villoutreix and Taboureau, 2015).

87 Thus, the estimation of the cardiac toxicity of organic hERG blockers is important theoretical and practical
88 task of medicinal chemistry (Obiol-Pardo et al., 2011). The quantitative structure – activity relationships
89 (QSARs) is a possible tool to predict the cardiac toxicity (Frid and Matthews, 2010). The aim of this
90 work is to build up QSAR models for the cardiac toxicity using the CORAL software
91 (<http://www.insilico.eu/coral>). Simplified molecular input-line entry system (SMILES) (Weininger, 1998,
92 1990; Weininger et al., 1989) is used to represent the molecular structure of examined organic hERG
93 blockers.

94

95 2. Method

96 2.1. Data.

97 The numerical data on cardiac toxicity (IC_{50} , half-maximal response dose (Obiol-Pardo et al., 2011), the
98 endpoint is pIC_{50} , i.e. the negative decimal logarithm of the IC_{50}) for 400 compounds taken in the
99 literature (Obiol-Pardo et al., 2011). These four hundred compounds are distributed into three sets: the
100 training set ($\approx 73\%$), the calibration set ($\approx 13.5\%$), and the external validation set ($\approx 13.5\%$). The
101 distributions are prepared according to the following principles: (i) these distributions are random; (ii)
102 these distributions are different; and (iii) the range of the endpoint for the training, calibration, and
103 validation sets are similar.

104

105 2.2. Optimal descriptors

106 Optimal descriptors, which are involved to build up the QSAR model for the pIC_{50} , are the following:

$$107 \quad DCW(T^*, N^*) = \Sigma \{ CW(s_k) + CW(ss_k) + CW(sss_k) \} + CW(BOND) + CW(NOSP) + CW(HALO) + CW(PAIR) \quad (1)$$

108 In Eq. 1, the s_k , ss_k , and sss_k are combinations of one, two, and three “SMILES atoms”. The “SMILES
109 atom” is a fragment of the SMILES notation, which contains one symbol or two symbols, which cannot
110 be examined separately (e.g. ‘Cl’, ‘Br’, etc.). The $CW(s_k)$, $CW(ss_k)$, and $CW(sss_k)$ are correlation weights
111 of the above-mentioned “SMILES atoms”. The correlation weights are coefficients, which used to

112 calculate the descriptor. The numerical data for the correlation weights are obtained by the Monte Carlo
113 method optimization procedure, which gives maximum of correlation coefficient between endpoint and
114 the optimal descriptor. The BOND, NOSP, HALO, and PAIR are global attributes of SMILES which
115 reflects the presence of various kinds of chemical bonds (BOND); the presence of nitrogen, oxygen,
116 sulphur, and phosphorus (NOSP); the presence of halogens, i.e. fluorine, chlorine, bromine, and iodine
117 (HALO); and presence of various combinations of SMILES atoms. The $CW(BOND)$, $CW(NOSP)$,
118 $CW(HALO)$, and $CW(PAIR)$ are correlation weights of the global attributes of SMILES. The detailed
119 description of the above listed local (s_k , ss_k , and sss_k) and global (BOND, NOSP, HALO, and PAIR)
120 attributes of SMILES is available in the literature (Toropova et al., 2015) as well as at web site of the
121 CORAL software (CORAL, 2015).

122 The T is the threshold, i.e. a coefficient used to classify SMILES attributes into two classes (i) rare or
123 noise; and (ii) active. The rare attributes are blocked (their correlation weights are fixed zero). The
124 coefficient can be 1, 2, ..., M. The T* is threshold which gives preferable statistical quality of the model
125 for the calibration set. The N is the number of epochs of the Monte Carlo optimization. The N* is the
126 number which gives preferable statistical quality for the calibration set. The T* and N* are calculated
127 according to scheme suggested in works (Toropova et al., 2015). Having the numerical data for the
128 correlation weights, one can calculate the $DCW(T^*, N^*)$ for the training set and define regression
129 parameters C_0 and C_1 for the following model

$$130 \quad pIC_{50} = C_0 + C_1 \times DCW(T^*, N^*) \quad (2)$$

131 The predictive potential of the model calculated with Eq. 2 should be checked up with external validation
132 set (Toropova et al., 2015).

133

134 **3. Results and Discussion**

135 *3.1. QSAR models*

136 The Monte Carlo optimization with T* and N* which are selected according to scheme suggested in work
137 (Toropova et al., 2015) gives the following models:

138

$$139 \quad pIC_{50} = -5.5431(\pm 0.0035) + 0.1418(\pm 0.0001) * DCW(1,22) \quad (3)$$

140

$$141 \quad pIC_{50} = -5.4618(\pm 0.0036) + 0.1331(\pm 0.0001) * DCW(1,17) \quad (4)$$

142

$$143 \quad pIC_{50} = -5.5541(\pm 0.0033) + 0.1527(\pm 0.0001) * DCW(1,28) \quad (5)$$

144

145 Table 1 contains the statistical characteristics of the models for pIC_{50} calculated with Eqs. 3-5. Figure 1
146 contains the graphical representation of these models.

147 Table 2 contains comparison of the predictive potential of models suggested here with the models
148 described in the literature. In fact, the only one model (Tan et al., 2012) is characterized by larger
149 determination coefficient, in comparison with models calculated with Eqs. 3-5. However, the above-
150 mentioned model (Tan et al., 2012) related to 133 compounds, whereas the models calculated with Eqs.
151 3-5 are related to 400 compounds.

152 [Table 1 around here]

153 [Table 2 around here]

154 [Figure 1 around here]

155 3.2. Mechanistic interpretation

156 Table 3 contains the list of molecular features, which are statistically stable promoters of increase or
157 decrease of the pIC_{50} . These data selected according to the following principles: (i) molecular features
158 extracted from SMILES with large prevalence in the training and calibration sets; (ii) molecular features
159 which have positive correlation weights for all three runs of the Monte Carlo optimization; and (iii)
160 molecular features which have negative correlation weights for all three runs of the Monte Carlo
161 optimization.

162 One can see, there are stable promoters of the pIC_{50} increase related to all distributions. For instance, (i)
163 presence of nitrogen together with oxygen (NOSP11000000); (ii) absence of halogens (HALO00000000);
164 and (iii) presence aromatic fragments (c...c...c...). Also there are stable promoters of the pIC_{50} decrease:
165 (i) branching of molecular skeleton i.e. brackets “(.....)”; (ii) presence of oxygen with double bonds
166 (O...=.....); and (iii) branching on nitrogen atoms (N...(.....)).

167 3.3. Domain of applicability

168 In fact, the basis of QSAR models is a list of eclectic data (Toropov et al., 2013a, 2013b; Toropova and
169 Toropov, 2015; Toropov and Toropova, 2014, 2015). These data is a list of parameters and/or conditions.
170 Building up a model can be accompanied by probabilistic characteristics of the influence of the parameters
171 and/or conditions upon endpoint (Toropova and Toropov, 2013; Toropov et al., 2012).

172 An example of the probabilistic parameter is a statistical defect of an attribute. The defect can be calculated
173 as the following:

174

$$175 \text{defect}(A_k) = \frac{P_T(A_k) - P_C(A_k)}{N_T(A_k) + N_C(A_k)} \quad (6)$$

176

177 where $P_T(A_k)$ and $P_C(A_k)$ are probabilities of attribute A_k in the training and the calibration set,
178 respectively; $N_T(A_k)$ and $N_C(A_k)$ are prevalence of the attribute A_k in the training and the calibration set,
179 respectively. It should be noted if $N_C(A_k) = 0$ then the $defect_k = 1$.

180 The criterion to define the domain of applicability is the following: SMILES falls into domain of
181 applicability if $defect(SMILES)$ calculated with Eq. 7 is less than average value of defects of SMILES
182 over the training set (inequality 8).

$$183 \quad defect(SMILES) = \sum defect(A_k) \quad (7)$$

$$184 \quad defect(SMILES) < 2 * \overline{defect(SMILES)} \quad (8)$$

185 According to criteria calculated with Eq. 7 and inequality 8, the distribution 1, 2, and 3 have 12 (22%), 7
186 (12%), and 9 (18%) outliers, respectively.

187 The sum of $defect(SMILES)$ is a measure of a distribution defect (DD):

$$188 \quad DD = \sum_{Training+Calibration} defect(SMILES) \quad (9)$$

189 The suggested criteria (Eqs. 6-9) are calculated with data on the training and calibration sets without any
190 data on the external validation set. Table 1 contains the DD values for three distribution examined in this
191 work.

192 Our hypothesis is: if the first distribution D1 is characterized by the distribution defect = DD1 and
193 distribution D2 is characterized by the distribution defect = DD2, then the distribution D1 is better than
194 distribution D2 if DD1 is smaller than DD2. Figure 2 contains graphical representations of correlations
195 between DD and statistical characteristics of models for distributions 1, 2, and 3.

196 [Figure 2 around here]

197 *Supplementary materials* section contains the correlation weights of stable promoters of increase or
198 decrease for cardiac toxicity (Table S1) and three distribution into the training, calibration, and validation
199 sets examined in this work together with experimental and calculated values of pIC_{50} , and domain of
200 applicability according to inequality 8 (Table S2).

201

202 **4. Conclusions**

203 The suggested models for cardiac toxicity have quite good statistical quality. The additional checking up
204 of the approach by means of comparison of three different distribution into the training, calibration, and
205 validation sets confirm the reproducing of the statistical quality for the three random event: i.e. building
206 up the QSAR model for random splits. The suggested models have mechanistic interpretation via groups
207 of promoters of increase/decrease for pIC_{50} . Finally, the special criteria for domain of applicability and

208 quality of distribution into the training and validation sets are defined for the approach. Thus, the approach
209 gives models in accordance with OECD principles (OECD, 2007).

210 **Acknowledgements**

211 AAT expresses gratitude to EC project PROSIL funded under the LIFE program (project
212 LIFE12ENV/IT/000154).

213 **References**

214

- 215 Anwar-Mohamed, A., Barakat, K.H., Bhat, R., Noskov, S.Y., Lorne Tyrrell, D., Tuszynski, J.A.,
216 Houghton, M., 2014. A human ether-á-go-go-related (hERG) ion channel atomistic model
217 generated by long supercomputer molecular dynamics simulations and its use in predicting drug
218 cardiotoxicity. *Toxicology Letters* 230, 382-392.
- 219 Cianchetta, G., Li, Y., Kang, J., Rampe, D., Fravolini, A., Cruciani, G., Vaz, R.J., 2005. Predictive
220 models for hERG potassium channel blockers. *Bioorganic & Medicinal Chemistry Letters* 15,
221 3637-3642.
- 222 CORAL software, 2015. <http://www.insilico.eu/coral>, Accessed November 17, 2015
- 223 Du-Cuny, L., Chen, L., Zhang, S., 2011. A critical assessment of combined ligand- and structure-based
224 approaches to HERG channel blocker modeling. *Journal of Chemical Information and Modeling*
225 51, 2948-2960.
- 226 Frid, A.A., Matthews, E.J., 2010. Prediction of drug-related cardiac adverse effects in humans-B: Use of
227 QSAR programs for early detection of drug-induced cardiac toxicities. *Regulatory Toxicology and*
228 *Pharmacology* 56, 276-289.
- 229 Obiol-Pardo, C., Gomis-Tena, J., Sanz, F., Saiz, J., Pastor, M., 2011. A multiscale simulation system
230 for the prediction of drug-induced cardiotoxicity. *Journal of Chemical Information and Modeling*
231 51 (2), 483-492.
- 232 Obrezanova, O., Csanyi, G., Gola, J.M., Segall, M.D., 2007. Gaussian processes: a method for
233 automatic QSAR modeling of ADME properties. *Journal of Chemical Information and Modeling*
234 47, 1847-1857.
- 235 OECD environment health and assessment No. 69 (2007). OECD Environment Health and Safety
236 Publications Series on Testing and Assessment No. 69, 2007. Guidance Document on the Validation
237 of (Quantitative) Structure-Activity Relationship [(Q)SAR] Models.
238 <<http://search.oecd.org/officialdocuments/>>(accessed 24.10.15).
- 239 Park, M.J., Lee, K.-R., Shin, D.-S., Chun, H.-S., Kim, C.-H., Ahn, S.-H., Bae, M.A., 2013. Predicted drug-
240 induced bradycardia related cardio toxicity using a zebrafish in vivo model is highly correlated
241 with results from in vitro tests. *Toxicology Letters* 216, 9-15.
- 242 Perry, M., Sanguinetti, M., Mitcheson, J., 2010. Symposium review: revealing the structural basis of
243 action of hERG potassium channel activators and blockers. *Journal of Physiology* 588, 3157-3167.
- 244 Seierstad, M., Agrafiotis, D.K., 2006. A QSAR model of HERG binding using a large, diverse, and
245 internally consistent training set. *Chemical Biology & Drug Design* 67, 284-296.

246 Sinha, N., Sen, S., 2011. Predicting hERG activities of compounds from their 3D structures:
247 development and evaluation of a global descriptors based QSAR model. *European Journal of*
248 *Medicinal Chemistry* 46, 618–630.

249 Tan, Y., Chen, Y., You, Q., Sun, H., Li, M., 2012. Predicting the potency of hERG K⁺ channel
250 inhibition by combining 3D-QSAR pharmacophore and 2D-QSAR models. *Journal of Molecular*
251 *Modeling* 18, 1023–1036.

252 Toropov, A.A., Toropova, A.P., Benfenati, E., Gini, G., Puzyn, T., Leszczynska, D., Leszczynski, J.,
253 2012. Novel application of the CORAL software to model cytotoxicity of metal oxide nanoparticles
254 to bacteria *Escherichia coli*. *Chemosphere* 89, 1098–1102.

255 Toropov, A.A., Toropova, A.P., Benfenati, E., Gini, G., Leszczynska, D., Leszczynski, J., 2013a.
256 CORAL: QSPR model of water solubility based on local and global SMILES attributes.
257 *Chemosphere* 90, 877-880.

258 Toropov, A.A., Toropova, A.P., Puzyn, T., Benfenati, E., Gini, G., Leszczynska, D., Leszczynski, J.,
259 2013b. QSAR as a random event: Models for nanoparticles uptake in PaCa2 cancer cells.
260 *Chemosphere* 92, 31–37.

261 Toropov, A.A., Toropova, A.P., 2014. Optimal descriptor as a translator of eclectic data into endpoint
262 prediction: Mutagenicity of fullerene as a mathematical function of conditions. *Chemosphere* 104,
263 262-264.

264 Toropov, A.A., Toropova, A.P., 2015. Quasi-QSAR for mutagenic potential of multi-walled carbon-
265 nanotubes. *Chemosphere* 124, 40–46.

266 Toropova, A.P., Toropov, A.A., 2013. Optimal descriptor as a translator of eclectic information into
267 the prediction of membrane damage by means of various TiO₂ nanoparticles. *Chemosphere* 93,
268 2650–2655.

269 Toropova, A.P., Toropov, A.A., 2015. Quasi-SMILES and nano-QFAR: United model for
270 mutagenicity of fullerene and MWCNT under different conditions. *Chemosphere* 139, 18–22.

271 Toropova, A.P., Toropov, A.A., Benfenati, E., Leszczynska, D., Leszczynski, J., 2015. QSAR model
272 as a random event: A case of rat toxicity. *Bioorganic and Medicinal Chemistry* 23 (6), 1223-1230.

273 Villoutreix, B.O., Taboureau, O., 2015. Computational investigations of hERG channel blockers: New
274 insights and current predictive models. *Advanced Drug Delivery Reviews* 86, 72-82.

275 Weininger, D., 1988. SMILES, a chemical language and information system. 1. Introduction to
276 methodology and encoding rules. *Journal of Chemical Information and Computer Sciences* 28,
277 31-36.

278 Weininger, D., Weininger, A., Weininger, J.L., 1989. SMILES. 2. Algorithm for generation of unique
279 SMILES notation. *Journal of Chemical Information and Computer Sciences* 29, 97-101.

280 Weininger, D., 1990. Smiles. 3. Depict. Graphical depiction of chemical structures. Journal of Chemical
281 Information and Computer Sciences 30, 237-243.

282

283

284 Table 1

285 The statistical characteristics of QSAR models for organic hERG blockers, calculated with Eqs. 3-5

286

Distribution	n _{train}	r ² _{train}	q ² _{train}	S _{train}	n _{calib}	r ² _{calib}	S _{calib}	n _{valid}	r ² _{valid}	S _{valid}	DD
1, Eq.3	294	0.9446	0.9440	0.283	52	0.7583	0.518	54	0.8618	0.396	342.8
2, Eq.4	290	0.9353	0.9345	0.301	54	0.8843	0.410	56	0.9359	0.298	327.7
3, Eq.5	299	0.9469	0.9463	0.265	51	0.9464	0.295	50	0.9035	0.343	337.6

287

288

289

290

291
292
293
294
295
296

Table 2

Comparison of the statistical quality of QSAR models for organic hERG blockers

Reference	n	r ²	s
Cianchetta et al., 2005	882	0.77	-
Seierstad and Agrafiotis, 2006	439	0.52	-
Obrezanova et al., 2007	137	0.81	-
Perry et al., 2010	400	0.52	-
Sinha and Sen, 2011	157	0.73	-
Du-Cuny et al., 2011	529	0.59	-
Obiol-Pardo et al., 2011.	400	0.52	0.89
Tan et al., 2012	113	0.90	-
In this work			
Split 1	400	0.916	0.34
Split 2	400	0.927	0.32
Split 3	400	0.942	0.28

297
298
299
300

Split 1

Eq. 3

Split 2

Eq. 4

Split 3

Eq. 5

Training set (\circ); Calibration set (\odot); Validation set (\bullet)

301

302 Figure 1

303 Graphical representation of models for cardiac toxicity calculated with Eqs. 3-5

304

305

306 Figure 2

307 Correlations between the distributions defects (DD) and statistical characteristics for the corresponding

308 validation sets (distributions are indicated by digits).